

INSURANCE CONTRACT AFTER PAYMENT OF INSURANCE

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Abstract: Any commercial organization offers several types of goods and services or profit from the production or sale of works operates in Therefore, general economic activity- accounting of goods, work or services income from the sale of mats and this product, work or service mats work release for gone of expenses account practiceto increase understood. It is known that in accounting goods, the work and somethingof mats to be sold their lowering to the situation or right to be paidto the situation in accounting.

Keywords: Insurance contract, insurance premium, money funds.

Insurance organization known right in return his own water gurta services shows. Uzbekistan Republic Citizenship Code of the insurance contract, unless otherwise provided If not, the insurance premium is paid or premium if paid in installments, effective after the first payment is made enters. So, this the situation goods sell process with equal tofor the provision of insurance services, the insurance organization the account of sale is taken only in the condition of payment of their fees going possible

Insurance contract after payment of insurance premium insurance under direct insurance as applicableof awards revenue 6280 "Straight away insurance conditionalmalari according to insurance awards". take will go In this this account At the checkout money funds account receiver accounts (5000), Accounts that record funds in foreign currency (5200), Accountant of funds in the settlement account accounts (5100) with correspondence possible For

example,

Debit 5010 (5110,5210) – Credit 6280

It is known that insurance premiums are mutually agreed upon at the time it's not, known periods between being to be paid too wax grudge will be This is it in case the insured of the award one shortmini from paying after different reasons according to insurance contract to file an application for termination, or the insured gurta award own on time non-payment due to contract own strength loss and insurer paid insurance awards-to proportional respectively obligation take to go possible Such cases too come fell insurance awards 6280 on the account reflection Made and periodically paid premiums each payment when increased account take will go

From the above except 6280 account credit according to below-gi accounts with too correspondence can:

- to the insured payable accounts (6030);
- payable dividends account receiver accounts (6610);
- employees with work right according to calculations account receiver accounts (6710).

The following wire through insurance of the organization own employees by they are with Created insurance to the contract basically paid insurance awards reflection delivered:

Debit 6710 – Credit 6280

Dividends to the founders through the following link in return they are with Created insurance contracts according to insurance awards holding to stay reflection delivered:

Debit 6610 – Credit 6280

Insurance by an insurance organization through this wiring coating in payment the insured by unpaid insurance of the award holding stay reflection delivered:

3.1. Full not formalized insurance contracts according to insurance awards account get

Under insurance contracts that are not fully formalized before stopping on the procedure for calculating insurance premiums insurance contract clearance order seeing exit to the goal according to is considered

The insurance contract is a written or oral agreement of the insured that application basically is made. Insurance of the contract written form not being formed in is expressed by its lack of force. Summer- which does not require the conclusion of an insurance contract in any form An exception is the state compulsory insurance. This-terms and procedure of insurance, insurer and insured girls legislation based on is determined.

Insurance contract in making the insured the following-

to must:

- to list all insured objects, if life insurance if all insured persons counting transition;

- the insurance event provided for in the insurance contract of your heart character about information to give

- the value of the insured object in property insurance or proprietary of interests maximum value show;

- occurrence of an insurance event on the insured object to the insurer of all factors affecting the probability show

If, after the conclusion of the insurance contract, the insurance event- the probability of damage or the amount of damage caused by it - Factors influencing lie on the part of the insured if it is known that it was delivered to the insurer, the insurance demand to cancel the insurance contract before the deadline reach to the right have

Proprietary insurance contract in making insurer property inspection or

determination of its true value has the right to attract special experts. live life bragging contract in making insurer insured-medicine in order to determine the true state of health apparently to pass Demand reach possible

When the parties conclude an insurance contract, the insured objects-list of, types of insurance events, insurance amount and mutual agreement regarding the validity period of the insurance contract they need to reach a compromise. These listed conditions are insurance considered important terms of the contract, the insurance contract- in of course given to be legislation based on Demand will be done.

When determining the insurance amount of the insured object, this if the sum insured exceeds the value of the insured object for the sake of it attention focus necessary.

There are two main types of determining the real value of property there is:

First, the date of conclusion of the property insurance contract is to get the balance sheet value. This value is on the balance sheet of the property value and legislation based on to him calculated of wear and tear again assessment account received in case difference based on is considered

In the second method, the purchase of the insured property Jats wear out account received without value is determined.

The value of the insured object, the insurance contract was concluded- cannot be changed after, only the object's by the insured in the assessment of the insurer distraction cases face gave circumstances from this except

Entrepreneurship risks in insurance insurance amount lead to hang possible has been insurance damage maximum from the volume increased can't go If in property insurance or business risk in insurance insurance amount reach possible has been water if the maximum amount of insurance damage is exceeded, the insurance must name exceeds the maximum insured loss of

the sum insured-rock in the part to power have won't be.

life insurance and civil liability insurance, su- gurta amount of the parties mutually agreement basically is determined.

Issued by the insured about the object of insured data and taking into account the probability of an insurance event without insurer insurance contract based on payable insurance of the award amount and to pay order defines.

Insurance contract of the insured application based on two bilaterally signed contract or insurer side-by issuing an insurance policy to the insured sh possible Insurance policy received person insurance conditions and requirements with agree that manifestation is enough.

Insurance in the contract insurance conditions and requirements water approved by the insurer and approved by the Ministry of Finance insurance control was deposited by the state inspection insurance in the rules determination possible In this insurance condition are indicated on the back of the insurance policy or separately attached to the contract. Also, the insurer and standard insurance contract in case of mutual agreement between the parties contract with changes to some aspects of make up too possible

Insurance in the rules above given of insurance mu-him from the conditions except the following given to be must:

- mutual obligations of the parties under the insurance contract riyats, as well as insurance contract according to payments done increase according to obligations;

- the insured by insurance of the event face to give it is true that events affecting the probability have occurred in to the insurer message to give order and conditions;

- insurance event provided for in the insurance contract- of happen that it was about to the insurer message to give spread tibi and conditions;

- providing insurance coverage under the insurance contract about claims seeing exit and him to pay refuse reach conditionlari and order;

- insurance of the contract to the conditions changes or addadditions input order;

- premature cancellation of the insurance contract tibi and conditions.

Insurance contract from the period specified in it or su- the insurance premium is effective from the date of payment. But insurance receiver insurance award without being paid before insurance event facegave in case insurance responsibility take doesn't go

Some insurance organizations issue insurance policies- rishin the following order done by increasing they go

Generally, an insurance policy is insurance by the insured on the basis of the application on the conclusion of the contractwill be This application is prepared in two copies. A copy of it remains with the insurance organization, and the second is the insurance premium it will be returned to the insured, indicating the procedures. The insured pays the insurance premium to the insurance organization.di. Insurance award from paid after defined in term the insurance organization issues an insurance policy andto the nucchi present is enough.

In this case, receiving the insurance premium is as followswire based on account is taken:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 6330

"From the insured received blob insurance awards"

Registration of the insurance policy and to the insured present to be done the following wire with account is taken;

Credit 6330 "Bundle insurance received from the insured awards" – Credit 6280

Conducting wiring in this way, usually, insurance- ta organizations by

loads in insurance done increased. Because in this case, an application for cargo insurance After the shipment, inspect the cargo for the insurance company. ziz and belongs to information take for time Demand will be done.

This-say to information the following to bring can:

- load sure name, his wrap weight and size;
- date of bill of lading and other shipping documents and numbers;
- transport type (sea in transport of the ship tonnage and built year date);
- the load dispatch order;
- the load dispatch the date and the risk evaluation for necessary another

data.

In most cases, the insured answers all questions at the same time he cannot find the answer in himself. At the same time, the insurance contract effective upon payment. that is why based on preliminary information provided by insurance organizations initial insurance after calculating the initial insurance premium contract make up possible Such of the contract main condition is that the insured during the specified period of time information that allows the policyholder to determine the level of insurance risk must provide information. This information is provided by after the final insurance premium is calculated and daily insurance contract is made.

If the insured by necessary data present

if not or the insured insurance award to pay refuse

if the insurance contract is not concluded and the insurance will be refunded. It is also considered final if the insurance premium is less than the initial insurance premium, or tick amount to the insured back is given.

Above given events in accounting reflection carry on order seeing we go out

After the conclusion of the initial insurance contract, the insurance the applicant must pay a certain amount of insurance premium. Maz-in the event

that the insurance contract is not fully formalized -that account take the following the lead to give can:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 6330

"From the insured received blob insurance awards"

If an insurance contract is not concluded, insurance premiums are to the boaster complete returns:

Debit 6330 "Insurance received from policyholders awards" – Credit 5000 (5100,5200)

If the final insurance contract is concluded and the excess is paid refundable if the insurance premium is required to be refunded to the sum above wire done is increased.

At the same time, with the conclusion of the final insurance contract insurance award to the amount the following wire given:

Debit 6330 – Credit 6280

If the insurance after the conclusion of the final insurance contract if the premium is more than the initial premium, the and for the missing amount, the following pro- vodka done is increased:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 6280.

In the insurance contract concluded with the insurance organization, su- insurance contract for the entire merchandise turnover of the insured it is possible for the accident to be transferred to the insured grudge Bonak's complete to the amount as follows wire given:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 6330

Later, each batch of goods is issued a po-in lis shown to the sum of the spot volume is reduced by:

Debit 6330 – Credit 6280

At the end of the term of the general insurance contract, the deposit-of unused amount back to the insured given:

Debit 6330 – Credit 5000 (5100,5200)

In some cases, insurance contracts under the main policy-at the end of the term of the contract relative to the deposit balance An agreed percentage of income can also be calculated. Percent- s designation to indebtedness special respectively done is increased but deposit the remainder debt as account not available.

It is known that insurance agents own activities only himself it's not, but also through insurance agents and brokers possible If the task of the insurance agent is only to To find the driver, take it to the insurance company to conclude a contract perform additional calculations on them when they arrive to increase Demand done it would be.

But it is concluded between the insurer and the insurance agent based on the mutual agency agreement, the insurance agent of on behalf insurance contract make up and own authority circle determining the amounts of insurance premiums and lang insurance awards acceptance to do possible Insurance agent insurance awards of the insurer account to the number passing will give.

According to the law, an insurance contract if it contains other yes order mean not caught if insurance award paid- comes into force after In this case, the contract concluded with the insurance agent the date of payment of the insurance contract by the insured the date of transfer of the insurance premium to the insurance agent will be Therefore, the insurance premiums to the insurer come fell the date it's not, perhaps of the insured account number-the date received from as the date of payment of the insurance premium account is taken.

Insurance of awards come fall 6280 on the account account is carried out. But the payment of the insurance premium lib, still to the insurance company's cash register or account number in case of non-arrival, it is not

necessary to give them the following right is:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 6280

Insurance agent and brokers with calculations 6040 account "Insurance agents and to brokers payable accounts" and 4040 account "Insurance agents and from brokers removable in accounts".done increase to the goal according to

Therefore, the insurance contract by the insurance agent after notification of the conclusion of the insurance policyThe goal is to provide the following payment for the entire amount of the fee- to according to:

Debit 4040 – Credit 6280

According to the agency agreement, the insurance agent in date to the insurer insurance award passing will give:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 4040

Based on the agency contract, the insurance agentAs the machine is built, the corresponding commission will receive the rewards. The commission will be added to the sum of the awards as follows: will:

Debit 2010 "Insurance work conduct expenses" – Credit 6040

The insurance premiums actually paid are shown below through account is taken:

Debit 6040 – Credit 5000 (5100,5200)

If insurance to the agent own commission awards himself accountlashing permission given if insurance agent come fell insurance deduct the corresponding commission from the awards can transfer it to the insurance organization. This In the case of commissions, the following pro- vodkas through done is increased:

Debit 4040 – Credit 6280

Transferred insurance award to the amount as follows wiregiven:

Debit 5000 (5100,5200) – Credit 4040

Insurance to the agent payable commission to the award below-the night wire to give through is:

Debit 2010 – Credit 6040

Insurance agent by this left commission muco-photo to the amount the following in order from the account is released:

Debit 6040 – Credit 4040

This condition insurance brokers with to be in calculationstoo observed.

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